

Filename: Nextera_DNA_Library 1_12.HSD5000

Default image (Contrast 50%), Image is Scaled to Sample

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Sample Info

Well	Conc. [pg/ul]	Sample Description	Alert	Observations
L1	2750	Ladder		Ladder
A4	10500	1np		
L2	2680	Ladder		Ladder
B4	5630	2np		

C4	34300	3np		
D4	6140	4np		
E4	7820	5np		
F4	4140	6np		
G4	3300	7np		
H4	5450	8np		
A5	7000	9np		
B5	1090	10np		
C5	7620	11np		
D5	99.9	12np		
A6	58.2	1n	▲	Marker(s) not detected
B6	20500	2n	▲	Marker(s) not detected
C6	96.1	3n	▲	Marker(s) not detected
D6	8530	4n	▲	Marker(s) not detected
L3	2590	Ladder		Ladder
E6	21700	5n	▲	Marker(s) not detected
F6	10300	6n	▲	Marker(s) not detected
G6	15100	7n	▲	Marker(s) not detected
H6	19700	8n	▲	Marker(s) not detected
A7	23000	9n	▲	Marker(s) not detected
B7	6410	10n	▲	Marker(s) not detected
C7	7960	11n	▲	Marker(s) not detected
D7	8300	12n	▲	Marker(s) not detected

L1: Ladder

Sample Table

Well	Conc. [pg/μl]	Sample Description	Alert	Observations
L1	2750	Ladder		Ladder

Peak Table

Size [bp]	Calibrated Conc. [pg/μl]	Assigned Conc. [pg/μl]	Peak Molarity [pmol/l]	% Integrated Area	Peak Comment	Observations
15	396	-	40600	-		Lower Marker
100	280	-	4310	10.20		
250	326	-	2010	11.88		
400	340	-	1310	12.37		
600	360	-	923	13.10		
1000	335	-	515	12.18		
1500	279	-	286	10.14		
2500	284	-	175	10.34		
3500	292	-	128	10.63		
5000	251	-	77.3	9.15		
10000	180	180	27.7	-		Upper Marker

A4: 1np

Sample Table

Well	Conc. [pg/ul]	Sample Description	Alert	Observations
A4	10500	1np		

Peak Table

Size [bp]	Calibrated Conc. [pg/ul]	Assigned Conc. [pg/ul]	Peak Molarity [pmol/l]	% Integrated Area	Peak Comment	Observations
15	174	-	17800	-		Lower Marker
319	10300	-	49600	97.79		
3892	232	-	91.6	2.21		
10000	180	180	27.7	-		Upper Marker

L2: Ladder

Sample Table

Well	Conc. [pg/μl]	Sample Description	Alert	Observations
L2	2680	Ladder		Ladder

Peak Table

Size [bp]	Calibrated Conc. [pg/μl]	Assigned Conc. [pg/μl]	Peak Molarity [pmol/l]	% Integrated Area	Peak Comment	Observations
15	356	-	36500	-		Lower Marker
100	244	-	3750	9.12		
250	299	-	1840	11.18		
400	306	-	1180	11.44		
600	336	-	861	12.54		
1000	361	-	555	13.47		
1500	284	-	291	10.60		
2500	292	-	180	10.91		
3500	300	-	132	11.20		
5000	255	-	78.4	9.53		
10000	180	180	27.7	-		Upper Marker

B4: 2np

Sample Table

Well	Conc. [pg/ul]	Sample Description	Alert	Observations
B4	5630	2np		

Peak Table

Size [bp]	Calibrated Conc. [pg/ul]	Assigned Conc. [pg/ul]	Peak Molarity [pmol/l]	% Integrated Area	Peak Comment	Observations
15	229	-	23400	-		Lower Marker
331	1690	-	7840	29.96		
527	1310	-	3820	23.23		
915	1550	-	2610	27.53		
1094	1090	-	1530	19.28		
10000	180	180	27.7	-		Upper Marker

C4: 3np

Sample Table

Well	Conc. [pg/ul]	Sample Description	Alert	Observations
C4	34300	3np		

Peak Table

Size [bp]	Calibrated Conc. [pg/ul]	Assigned Conc. [pg/ul]	Peak Molarity [pmol/l]	% Integrated Area	Peak Comment	Observations
15	44.7	-	4580	-		Lower Marker
345	34300	-	153000	100.00		
10000	180	180	27.7	-		Upper Marker

D4: 4np

Sample Table

Well	Conc. [pg/ul]	Sample Description	Alert	Observations
D4	6140	4np		

Peak Table

Size [bp]	Calibrated Conc. [pg/ul]	Assigned Conc. [pg/ul]	Peak Molarity [pmol/l]	% Integrated Area	Peak Comment	Observations
15	264	-	27100	-		Lower Marker
349	3060	-	13500	49.80		
537	1620	-	4640	26.40		
908	1460	-	2470	23.80		
10000	180	180	27.7	-		Upper Marker

E4: 5np

Sample Table

Well	Conc. [pg/ul]	Sample Description	Alert	Observations
E4	7820	5np		

Peak Table

Size [bp]	Calibrated Conc. [pg/ul]	Assigned Conc. [pg/ul]	Peak Molarity [pmol/l]	% Integrated Area	Peak Comment	Observations
15	273	-	28000	-		Lower Marker
346	3530	-	15700	45.09		
526	1940	-	5690	24.86		
889	2350	-	4070	30.05		
10000	180	180	27.7	-		Upper Marker

F4: 6np

Sample Table

Well	Conc. [pg/µl]	Sample Description	Alert	Observations
F4	4140	6np		

Peak Table

Size [bp]	Calibrated Conc. [pg/µl]	Assigned Conc. [pg/µl]	Peak Molarity [pmol/l]	% Integrated Area	Peak Comment	Observations
15	270	-	27700	-		Lower Marker
524	1130	-	3310	27.23		
897	1370	-	2340	33.01		
1228	1650	-	2060	39.76		
10000	180	180	27.7	-		Upper Marker

G4: 7np

Sample Table

Well	Conc. [pg/ul]	Sample Description	Alert	Observations
G4	3300	7np		

Peak Table

Size [bp]	Calibrated Conc. [pg/ul]	Assigned Conc. [pg/ul]	Peak Molarity [pmol/l]	% Integrated Area	Peak Comment	Observations
15	309	-	31700	-		Lower Marker
340	2210	-	9980	66.91		
1042	1090	-	1610	33.09		
10000	180	180	27.7	-		Upper Marker

H4: 8np

Sample Table

Well	Conc. [pg/ul]	Sample Description	Alert	Observations
H4	5450	8np		

Peak Table

Size [bp]	Calibrated Conc. [pg/ul]	Assigned Conc. [pg/ul]	Peak Molarity [pmol/l]	% Integrated Area	Peak Comment	Observations
15	263	-	27000	-		Lower Marker
352	2410	-	10500	44.24		
514	1390	-	4160	25.54		
877	1650	-	2890	30.23		
10000	180	180	27.7	-		Upper Marker

A5: 9np

Sample Table

Well	Conc. [pg/ul]	Sample Description	Alert	Observations
A5	7000	9np		

Peak Table

Size [bp]	Calibrated Conc. [pg/ul]	Assigned Conc. [pg/ul]	Peak Molarity [pmol/l]	% Integrated Area	Peak Comment	Observations
15	235	-	24100	-		Lower Marker
352	2570	-	11300	36.75		
535	2090	-	6010	29.86		
929	2340	-	3870	33.39		
10000	180	180	27.7	-		Upper Marker

B5: 10np

Sample Table

Well	Conc. [pg/ul]	Sample Description	Alert	Observations
B5	1090	10np		

Peak Table

Size [bp]	Calibrated Conc. [pg/ul]	Assigned Conc. [pg/ul]	Peak Molarity [pmol/l]	% Integrated Area	Peak Comment	Observations
15	176	-	18000	-		Lower Marker
1023	1090	-	1640	100.00		
10000	180	180	27.7	-		Upper Marker

C5: 11np

Sample Table

Well	Conc. [pg/ul]	Sample Description	Alert	Observations
C5	7620	11np		

Peak Table

Size [bp]	Calibrated Conc. [pg/ul]	Assigned Conc. [pg/ul]	Peak Molarity [pmol/l]	% Integrated Area	Peak Comment	Observations
15	189	-	19400	-		Lower Marker
359	2880	-	12400	37.80		
1088	4740	-	6700	62.20		
10000	180	180	27.7	-		Upper Marker

D5: 12np

Sample Table

Well	Conc. [pg/ul]	Sample Description	Alert	Observations
D5	99.9	12np		

Peak Table

Size [bp]	Calibrated Conc. [pg/ul]	Assigned Conc. [pg/ul]	Peak Molarity [pmol/l]	% Integrated Area	Peak Comment	Observations
15	419	-	43000	-		Lower Marker
222	99.9	-	691	100.00		
10000	180	180	27.7	-		Upper Marker

A6: 1n

Sample Table

Well	Conc. [pg/μl]	Sample Description	Alert	Observations
A6	58.2	1n	▲	Marker(s) not detected

Peak Table

Size [bp]	Calibrated Conc. [pg/μl]	Assigned Conc. [pg/μl]	Peak Molarity [pmol/l]	% Integrated Area	Peak Comment	Observations
-	51.9	-	-	89.18		
-	180	180	-	-		Upper Marker
-	6.30	-	-	10.82		

B6: 2n

Sample Table

Well	Conc. [pg/μl]	Sample Description	Alert	Observations
B6	20500	2n	▲	Marker(s) not detected

Peak Table

Size [bp]	Calibrated Conc. [pg/μl]	Assigned Conc. [pg/μl]	Peak Molarity [pmol/l]	% Integrated Area	Peak Comment	Observations
-	7400	-	-	36.01		
-	11900	-	-	57.75		
-	791	-	-	3.85		
-	491	-	-	2.39		
-	180	180	-	-		Upper Marker

C6: 3n

Sample Table

Well	Conc. [pg/μl]	Sample Description	Alert	Observations
C6	96.1	3n	▲	Marker(s) not detected

Peak Table

Size [bp]	Calibrated Conc. [pg/μl]	Assigned Conc. [pg/μl]	Peak Molarity [pmol/l]	% Integrated Area	Peak Comment	Observations
-	91.1	-	-	94.78		
-	180	180	-	-		Upper Marker
-	5.02	-	-	5.22		

D6: 4n

Sample Table

Well	Conc. [pg/µl]	Sample Description	Alert	Observations
D6	8530	4n	▲	Marker(s) not detected

Peak Table

Size [bp]	Calibrated Conc. [pg/µl]	Assigned Conc. [pg/µl]	Peak Molarity [pmol/l]	% Integrated Area	Peak Comment	Observations
-	2880	-	-	33.76		
-	5270	-	-	61.83		
-	377	-	-	4.42		
-	180	180	-	-		Upper Marker

L3: Ladder

Sample Table

Well	Conc. [pg/μl]	Sample Description	Alert	Observations
L3	2590	Ladder		Ladder

Peak Table

Size [bp]	Calibrated Conc. [pg/μl]	Assigned Conc. [pg/μl]	Peak Molarity [pmol/l]	% Integrated Area	Peak Comment	Observations
15	347	-	35600	-		Lower Marker
100	225	-	3460	8.67		
250	278	-	1710	10.72		
400	315	-	1210	12.17		
600	330	-	845	12.71		
1000	325	-	501	12.55		
1500	281	-	289	10.85		
2500	293	-	180	11.31		
3500	295	-	130	11.37		
5000	250	-	77.0	9.65		
10000	180	180	27.7	-		Upper Marker

E6: 5n

Sample Table

Well	Conc. [pg/µl]	Sample Description	Alert	Observations
E6	21700	5n	▲	Marker(s) not detected

Peak Table

Size [bp]	Calibrated Conc. [pg/µl]	Assigned Conc. [pg/µl]	Peak Molarity [pmol/l]	% Integrated Area	Peak Comment	Observations
-	6390	-	-	29.40		
-	14200	-	-	65.26		
-	529	-	-	2.43		
-	632	-	-	2.91		
-	180	180	-	-		Upper Marker

F6: 6n

Sample Table

Well	Conc. [pg/µl]	Sample Description	Alert	Observations
F6	10300	6n	▲	Marker(s) not detected

Peak Table

Size [bp]	Calibrated Conc. [pg/µl]	Assigned Conc. [pg/µl]	Peak Molarity [pmol/l]	% Integrated Area	Peak Comment	Observations
-	3220	-	-	31.37		
-	5700	-	-	55.47		
-	701	-	-	6.82		
-	651	-	-	6.34		
-	180	180	-	-		Upper Marker

G6: 7n

Sample Table

Well	Conc. [pg/μl]	Sample Description	Alert	Observations
G6	15100	7n	▲	Marker(s) not detected

Peak Table

Size [bp]	Calibrated Conc. [pg/μl]	Assigned Conc. [pg/μl]	Peak Molarity [pmol/l]	% Integrated Area	Peak Comment	Observations
-	3490	-	-	23.13		
-	10700	-	-	71.17		
-	378	-	-	2.51		
-	481	-	-	3.19		
-	180	180	-	-		Upper Marker

H6: 8n

Sample Table

Well	Conc. [pg/μl]	Sample Description	Alert	Observations
H6	19700	8n	▲	Marker(s) not detected

Peak Table

Size [bp]	Calibrated Conc. [pg/μl]	Assigned Conc. [pg/μl]	Peak Molarity [pmol/l]	% Integrated Area	Peak Comment	Observations
-	6450	-	-	32.76		
-	12200	-	-	62.13		
-	596	-	-	3.03		
-	411	-	-	2.09		
-	180	180	-	-		Upper Marker

A7: 9n

Sample Table

Well	Conc. [pg/µl]	Sample Description	Alert	Observations
A7	23000	9n	▲	Marker(s) not detected

Peak Table

Size [bp]	Calibrated Conc. [pg/µl]	Assigned Conc. [pg/µl]	Peak Molarity [pmol/l]	% Integrated Area	Peak Comment	Observations
-	5520	-	-	23.98		
-	16200	-	-	70.21		
-	800	-	-	3.47		
-	537	-	-	2.33		
-	180	180	-	-		Upper Marker

B7: 10n

Sample Table

Well	Conc. [pg/μl]	Sample Description	Alert	Observations
B7	6410	10n	▲	Marker(s) not detected

Peak Table

Size [bp]	Calibrated Conc. [pg/μl]	Assigned Conc. [pg/μl]	Peak Molarity [pmol/l]	% Integrated Area	Peak Comment	Observations
-	1650	-	-	25.69		
-	4770	-	-	74.31		
-	180	180	-	-		Upper Marker

C7: 11n

Sample Table

Well	Conc. [pg/μl]	Sample Description	Alert	Observations
C7	7960	11n	▲	Marker(s) not detected

Peak Table

Size [bp]	Calibrated Conc. [pg/μl]	Assigned Conc. [pg/μl]	Peak Molarity [pmol/l]	% Integrated Area	Peak Comment	Observations
-	2660	-	-	33.41		
-	5240	-	-	65.81		
-	62.1	-	-	0.78		
-	180	180	-	-		Upper Marker

D7: 12n

Sample Table

Well	Conc. [pg/ul]	Sample Description	Alert	Observations
D7	8300	12n	▲	Marker(s) not detected

Peak Table

Size [bp]	Calibrated Conc. [pg/ul]	Assigned Conc. [pg/ul]	Peak Molarity [pmol/l]	% Integrated Area	Peak Comment	Observations
-	7900	-	-	95.17		
-	180	180	-	-		Upper Marker
-	309	-	-	3.72		
-	92.2	-	-	1.11		